

REVIVING THE GANDHIAN ASHRAM PERSPECTIVE: A SUSTAINABLE PATHWAY ECOLOGY AND URBANISATION

Ankit*

Research scholar, Department of Gandhian Thought and Peace Studies,

School of Social Science, Central University of Gujarat, Kundhela,

Email Id: ankit.bu10@gmail.com

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Abstract

The environmental problems of the current urbanization that the cities face today are very different from those in Gandhi's era, but his concepts on development, gram swaraj, non-violence, self-reliant, Sarvodaya (welfare of all) and Antodaya (upliftment of the weakest) combined, make an ecologically conscious critique of the contemporary cities. Gandhi's thoughts inspired diverse streams of environmental philosophy, emphasizing harmony with nature, responsible resource use, and community-centric sustainability. By looking at the Gandhian ashram again as a model of sustainable community living, This paper defining the Gandhian ashram as a model of sustainable community living, explores how its concepts of simple living, zero or minimal waste, conservation of natural resources and shared responsibility can be the source of humane, low-impact urban growth models. the paper contends By examining the Ashram model through a Gandhian perspective, this paper contends that the return of the ashram model is a practical, value-based means leading to just and sustainable urbanisation in the present time.

Keywords: *Gandhi philosophy, Environment, Ashram Model, Urbanisation, Self-reliance.*

Introduction

The present world in which science, technology and development play a crucial role in changing human history. However, too much exploitation of natural resources in the name of development and human greed leads to a serious environmental problem. In fact, the idea of development is itself more controversial in the contemporary situation as it often justifies the unethical use of natural resources. It's rather common to encounter high dam controversies, deforestation, water disputes and air pollution these days. Eminent environmental activist 'Vandana Shiva argues that development is actually based on a continuation of colonialism.'

According to Gustavo Esteva, she argues that “development is a permanent war waged by its promoters and suffered by its victims” (Shiva, 1995). that a true science that does not respect nature’s needs and a development which does not respect people’s demands threatens human survival. The environment of Gandhi gives us a new vision to harmonise nature with the needs of people (Joshi, 2001).

Gandhi was far more than just a freedom fighter; his remarkable and charismatic personality encompassed many dimensions. His thoughts and teachings continue to hold deep relevance across the wide range. Including education, Socio-political, economics, science-tech, philosophy, value and ethics, global peace and harmony and Environmental sustainability. His visionary ideas consistently as an inspired and motivated people and shaping society (Dutta, 2023). He considers mother earth a living organism. He believed “that the universe was structured and informed by the cosmic spirit, that all men, all life and indeed all creation were one” (Parekh, 2001). Gandhi's lifelong experimentations with truth led him to develop all his ideas and thoughts, which makes Gandhian ideas even more relevant in modern time.

People's mobilization of the environment has increased in the last five decades or so. There have been environmental conventions all over the globe, for instance the "*Stockholm Conference*" held in 1972 and the "*Rio Earth Summit*" of 1992 (Giri, 2023). However, Gandhi voiced his concern for the environment in his different publications, speeches, and messages to the people about a decade ago (Dutta, 2023). It is important to keep in mind that he was not an environmentalist in the contemporary sense, but the implications of his socio-political and economic ideas make him an environmentalist. Though several environmentalist thinkers and movements in India have drawn inspiration from Gandhi.

Although Gandhi never employed words like "environment" or "ecology" a deep respect for nature was woven throughout his life, life, philosophy and work. Whether his idea of gram-swaraj, non-violence, khadi Charkha to his self-reliance, the presence and importance of the natural world were always in the heart of Gandhi. For this reason, Pravin Sheth said that "*World's Early Environmentalist in Vision and Practice*" in his work "*The Eco-Gandhi and Ecological Movements.*" Sundarlal Bahuguna, the leader of India's first successful environmental Chipko movement in 1973, and Medha Patekar, the leader of the Narmada Bachao campaign in the 1980s, were both inspired by Gandhi (Dutta, 2023).

Urban growth today is still very much dependent on technological advances, scientific innovations, and the fast-paced economies of the world. However, the kind of growth that has been expanding lately tends to harm ecosystems and in addition, the rich get richer while the

poor get poorer. The large-scale infrastructure endeavors such as dams, deforestation, air pollution as well as the contamination of water sources are some of the ways in which the use of resources is shown to be in favor of profit over people - a pattern that scholars like Vandana Shiva attribute to the ancestral colonial ways whereby advancement meant the displacement of both human populations and habitats.

Comparatively, Gandhi's ashram conception offers another way: it rests on the pillars of nature protection, community-managed systems, and sharing human needs without going beyond the planet's limits. His concepts - gram swaraj (local rule), ahimsa (non-harm), simple living, and Sarvodaya (welfare for all) - implied small settlements which were self-governing and living in harmony with nature, perceiving land as a heritage from future generations, directing their production towards necessities rather than unlimited profit. The reintroduction of the ashram model in urban planning could be a localizing influence less city forms; thinking of big cities as groups of linked "city ashrams" communities-bond, almost-waste free activities could be the peaceful co-existence among people and their environment.

Gandhi's Environmentalist thoughts

Gandhi has not said anything specific on environmental issues, as in earlier times it was not a big concern and issue for mankind or society. The irony is that, whereas every responsible person appears to be aware and worried about pollution, no substantial remedy is in sight. Gandhi's have offered a new way of approach about how to balance human demands with the environment. His reflection about Satyagraha, simple living, and development showcase how society can grow in a way that it doesn't harm nature and other human beings (Giri, 2023). He has faith in *Advaita* philosophy of nonduality, which holds that man and all living things are inherently one. "Nature has enough to satisfy everyone's needs but not to satisfy anybody's greed," he said, and this became a key premise of modern environmentalism. Here, Gandhi's teachings provide some hope. When we see his literature, speech and writings, we find everything about it is ideas on the environment (Joshi, 2003).

Gandhi's book *Hind swaraj* 1909, is not only provided as a "critique of modern civilisation and Western industrialization but also an insightful work laying the groundwork for environmental consciousness. Although the term "environment" as we know it today was not in common use during Gandhi's era, the philosophies within *Hind Swaraj* contain key principles relevant to today's global ecological debates. Gandhi was deeply critical of modern civilisation, viewing it as a leading cause of environmental issues. He warned against the dangers of reckless and unplanned industrial and modernization growth, which he described as "Satanic" for its

unrelenting pursuit for material wealth and its incessant growth of desires. He believes that such activities led to widespread resource exploitation and upset the natural balance between humans, and the environment is highly relevant considering present-day fears about exhaustion of resources and environmental degradation. In the Morden tradition, human nature with environment is separated or conquerors, whereas in Indian tradition human nature with environment is interconnected and respectful. The ground was his mother and should be revered. Gandhi was deeply impacted by Indian tradition and emphasized simple living and high thinking. Gandhi believed that “*the Earth provides enough to satisfy human needs but not human greed*”, making a clear distinction between need and want. He argued that only by exercising self-restraint and limiting desires can humanity live in balance with nature, emphasized on the interdependence of all living things and promoted respect and awe for all beings, including plants, animals, and non-living things like rivers and mountains. The swaraj means self-rule extending to the ideas of gram swaraj, where villagers live in harmony and cooperation with natural resources sustain as a common and collective good.

Gandhi's autobiography “*The Story of My Experiments with Truth (1925-29)*” though primarily a spiritual, moral and ethical journey, gently represents his deep understanding of the environment. Through personal highlight, Gandhi proves how living simply-life, limiting one's needs/demands, and practicing self-restraint are essential for harmony with nature. His daily practicing vegetarianism, homespun clothing and minimal possessions, were expressions of both personal and environmental discipline. For example, Gandhi's prayer speech at Sambhal on 27th Dec 1947 he said “You must keep yourself clean externally and internally. Your village should be free of dirt and dung in every way. And it should be free from foul smells. You should follow the rules of sanitation” (Joshi, 2001). He motivates Indian villagers to sanitation and cleanliness of the environment (vol. 90, pp 305-307). Moreover, Gandhi once said, “Man has no power to create life, therefore, he has no right to destroy life” (Suchak., n.d.). Man has been endowed with superior faculties, helping him to experience compassion toward inferior beings.

Gandhi's book “*Key to Health (1948)*” highlights the environmental perspective focused on Natural Cure, and Gandhi's ideas of unity with all living beings, rooted in frugal natural resources use, aimed to contribute to a sustainable society through practical application of real-life concepts. He emphasises a close link between men and the environment. In ancient Indian culture, plants, rivers, mountains, sunlight, and so on, were considered holy and given great importance due to their health benefits. “The science of natural therapeutics is based on a use

of the same five elements, in the treatment of disease, which constitute the human body. These are earth, water, ether, sunlight and air... they can be utilized for health purposes” (Key to Health, pp.57-58).

This is also closely related to village life, which Gandhi strongly advocate for, 'My natural cure is designed solely for villagers and villages. There is no place in it for a microscope, X-ray, and similar things. Personal hygiene and healthy living are of primary importance' (Harijan, 11-8-1946). According to Gandhi, human's body asserts from five natural elements, the most significant among them air element. He disliked violating these elements that leads to an unhealthy lifestyle. (*Gandhi's views on nature and environment*, n.d.). His opinion in Harijan, 'Anyone who fouls the air by spitting about carelessly, throwing refuse and rubbish or otherwise dirtying the ground sins against man and nature. Man's body is the temple of God. Anyone who fouls the air that is to enter that temple desecrates it' (Harijan, 7-4-1946).

Gandhi deeply advocated for a simple and *Sattvic* (clean and healthy) diet as necessary for good health. He was a great believer in vegetarianism and strongly opposed eating meat. According to Gandhi, human beings are more than their physical bodies; the spirit and moral qualities are also noteworthy. He believed that humans were not naturally designed to eat meat, but rather to thrive on the fruits and plants that the earth frequently provides. Even when faced with illness, Gandhi refused to renounce his beliefs, instead staying to vegetarianism and natural healing treatments. His devotion to natural cure and unwillingness to consume meat can be interpreted as reflections of his deep compassion and commitment to nonviolence, not only toward other people, but toward all species that exist. For Gandhi, caring for one's health was inseparable to living gently and ethically on this earth, in harmony with both nature and the wider ecosystem of life.

Gandhi's Ashram Perspective

Gandhi's ashram model is based on his teaching to improve the human condition from spiritual, moral and ethical in contrast with the capitalistic form of humans. The ashram model is a perfect example of our contemporary civil society. Every person who lived in an ashram did their own duty. no inequality, injustice, no discrimination based on gender, race, colour, caste etc. as “each man doing their own duty” is a simple method to resolve a problem and issues in society. His ashram model also creates an oceanic influence theory to other people also throughout the change toward *individual* → *family* → *society* → *division* → *state* → *nation* and lastly at *universal level*. In this theory, focus is shifted on the smaller unit of the society, though ultimate change is being done to forward to the upper and hierarchical level and this

transformation is based on justified ends and its means. Gandhi established several ashrams throughout his life, both in India and South Africa. First Phoenix Settlement in Natal 1904, Second Tolstoy Farm outside Johannesburg in 1910, after Gandhi came to India, he established third Sabarmati Ashram outside Ahmedabad in 1915, and fourth Sevagram Ashram established in Wardha 1936 (Hardy, n.d.).

Many thinkers analyse Gandhi's ashram model in several of their works, according to Mark Thomson in his remarkable book *Gandhi's initiatives of ashram life thus: analysis* "The ashrams Gandhi established served as laboratories where he and his colleagues experimented with nonviolence as an alternative way of life. In these small monastic communities of men and women living according to absolute vows he sought to lay the groundwork for an egalitarian social organisation and economy, and to develop an education system that reflected Indian society. The ashrams model provided economic and moral support as well as fostering the discipline and awareness necessary for their members to sustain grassroot civil disobedience. Gandhi saw the need in the tradition-bound, rigidly hierarchical Indian society, for a moral sanction able to inspire people to help themselves. He believed ashramas life, based on mutuality, simplicity and hard work, would nurture an asceticism that could be channelled through positive action to reform society" (Thomson, 1993).

Gandhi's ideas of an ashram life were heavily influenced by John Ruskin's work and his strict vows of vegetarianism. He adhered to his moral principles throughout his life not only because of his family background and traditions, but because he kept his promise to his mother. In addition to his non-violent approach, this might have contributed to his success. Throughout his works, Leo Tolstoy emphasizes the importance of self-control and vegetarianism, which is reflected in Gandhi's ascetic lifestyle. Ashram life is based on eastern and Indian values, which align with Gandhi's ideas on cooperative communities. While living in South Africa, he participated in non-violent struggles against racial discrimination in cooperative communities. Community living allowed Gandhi to involve everyone in his life mission, extending his non-violence into all spheres of life (*Gandhi's ashrams: seed beds of ecological development*, n.d.).

Case study of Indian ecological movement

The Indian environmental movement in recent years has focused on a wide range of issues from waste management, climate change, environmental clearance, wildlife, and forest conservation to pollution, illegal mining and disposal of toxic wastes. To address those concerns, modern activists adopt Gandhian philosophy of nonviolence and community development for grassroot mobilization on eco-friendly governance. Modern environmental

movements are increasingly concerned with green politics and the conservation of natural resources. The history behind India's environmental movement is the rich tapestry of battles, protests and tenacity. From the colonial era of exploitation to the challenges of the globalization era and climate change, the progress has been markers in the sand and people's mobilization. As we analyse the growth of this movement, it becomes clear that Gandhi's values continue to inspire and inform the ongoing quest for ecological sustainability and social justice. Key concepts and principles of Gandhi's philosophy are Sarvodaya (welfare of all), satyagraha (force of truthness), ahimsa (non-violence), and self-sufficiency etc. As environmental activists apply Gandhian philosophy to contemporary environment movements, they can create a framework that addresses environmental concerns as well as promoting social justice, empowerment, and ethical engagement and sustainability with nature. some environmental movement related to Gandhian philosophy: -

Chipko Movement (1973): The Chipko movement was a protest against cutting trees in the Himalayan region, with women leading the charge. The term 'Chipko' means to hug trees, and this tactic was used to prevent their felling. The movement was fully inspired by the Gandhian philosophy of non-violence, satyagraha, which underlined the role of rural masses in environmental conservation. Chandika Prasad Bhatt proclaimed Gandhi as the spiritual patron of the movement and said, "Like Gandhiji, he calls for a break with the culture of domination and for redefining our roles in sharing the fruits of our toil with others, with one another and with nature" (Dash, 2014).

Narmada Bachao Andolan (1985): This movement emerged from Madhya Pradesh in 1985, Inspired by Gandhian concepts of justice and civil disobedience, the protesters sought to preserve values of human rights and ecological sustainability. Leaders such as Medha Patekar and Baba Amte remembered Gandhi's criticism of modern civilisation, large-scale development as they worked against the exploitation of tribal and rural people displaced by development projects. This generation looks for alternative, decentralized and environment-friendly sustainable ways, influenced by Gandhian philosophy (Moolakkattu J. S., 2019).

Silent Valley Movement (1970): this movement originated from Kerala in the late 1970s, The Silent Valley rainforest was saved by activists through Gandhian ethics forms of non-violent protest, public awareness, mass mobilization etc This holistic approach brought together a variety of interests, and reflected Gandhi's respect for all beings and the victory of values over short-term economic profit. The outcome of this movement shifted toward recognizing ecological stability (Sasikala, n.d.).

Rally for Rivers (2017): This movement mainly focuses to raise awareness about the politeness of India's rivers and promote sustainable water management. It reflects Gandhian values and philosophy of environmental conservation and collective responsibility toward helping to save natural resources.

Plastic Waste Management Campaigns: In India, there are several regional campaign initiatives aimed to create a plastic free environment, minimum and zero uses of plastic day to day uses. These movements promote Gandhian values of simplicity and self-reliance, encouraging communities to adopt eco-friendly practices.

Hence, these movements demonstrate how Gandhian philosophy continues to inspire environmental activism in India, promoting a holistic approach that combines ecological sustainability with social justice and community empowerment.

Contemporary Relevance of Gandhi's Environmental Perspective in Urbanisation

Gandhi's ecological vision, which was developed even before the concept of modern environmentalism, is very relevant to the urban crises of pollution, ecological degradation, and increasing inequalities that are happening today. His idea of living a simple life and controlling one's desires, as well as his saying that "nature provides for human needs, not for greed," could be a solution to the current problems of overconsumption, high-carbon lifestyles, and the brutal exploitation of urban and peri-urban ecosystems. his moral values of Sarvodaya (welfare of all) and Antyodaya (upliftment of the poorest) serve as the initial source of ideas for urban planning that is both environmentally friendly and socially inclusive. Such planning would also be a guarantee that the most vulnerable do not suffer from further marginalisation, e.g., lack of access to proper housing, transport, and resources.

Regarding his concept of non-violence (ahimsa), it is worth noting that Gandhi extended his love and care not only to humans but also to animals and the whole biodiversity. Therefore, the concern of dwindling green areas and vanishing species would be a call from him for cities to safeguard both the urban commons and the habitats of animals and ecological corridors since these are the means for just urbanisation. Among the many challenges that cities have to face such as climate shocks and supply chain disruptions, Gandhi's focus on village swaraj, decentralisation, and local self-reliance plays a crucial role in neighbourhood economies' resilience, local food systems' robustness, and community-managed resources' viability in cities and their outskirts. Moreover, his ashram experiments can be considered as the first models of a sustainable community-centred urban way of living.

After independence, the Indian environmental movements such as the Chipko Andolan, the Narmada Bachao Andolan, and the Silent Valley movement, which used Gandhian methods like non-violent direct action, bottom-up organising, and an ethical bond to land and water to fight against destructive mega-projects and extractive urban growth, clearly illustrate the continued effectiveness of these methods. Gandhi's doubt about too much mechanisation and industrialisation without proper consideration is very much in line with present-day discussions about the runaway ecological impact of growth-driven, automobile-centric and infrastructure-heavy urbanisation, which, in turn, point to the urgent need for humane, regenerative and low-impact technologies and designs. Moreover, his worry about hygiene, clean water, and public health, is very much alive in modern initiatives such as the Swachh Bharat Abhiyan, which not only focuses on clean cities but also demands deep behavioural and structural changes. Most importantly, his principle of personal accountability in everyday life, such as saving water and energy, and at the same time, acknowledging nature's inherent value, is still the core of a new urban citizenship model which is ecological citizenship.

Ultimately, Gandhi's environmental vision calls for the urban life to be infused again with care, simplicity and limits and, therefore, it answers the planetary urban crisis of today by saying that mere technical fixes will not do but rather a transformation of values, relationships and lifestyles will be required. Therefore, his concepts are not only relevant but they provide a transformative framework for cities to be just, sustainable, and peaceful for all beings.

Conclusion

The present environmental problems that the world is facing, many of which have been exacerbated by the rapid and unplanned urbanisation, require a sustainable solution that is both effective and immediate to guarantee the well-being and peaceful coexistence of all living beings. The Gandhian viewpoint has various valuable elements that can be used to handle these problems. It is not likely that the urban generations of today will be able to completely live a Spartan life, but the application of Gandhian logic and sensitivity in the designing of cities and the routine life can still make a big difference in saving the earth from destruction. Once the limits to greed and respect for nature are considered, environment-friendly science and technologies can be used without endangering nature in urban systems. Gandhi's ashram, which was centred around the ideas of simplicity, self-reliance, less waste, and sharing the responsibility, is a viable scheme that can be extended from small, community units, to larger urban structures and thus be instrumental in getting the people involved in protecting natural ecosystems. Currently, administrations are mirroring some features of this approach through

various projects that aim at improving sanitation, clean water, and public health in urban areas, e.g. the Swachh Bharat Abhiyan (Clean India Campaign) and the initiatives such as the odd-even traffic scheme that helps in lowering the air pollution in cities. When they are looked at as a whole, these instances indicate that Gandhi's concepts are still quite valid in the environment of modern, rapidly urbanising societies and therefore can be a great help in solving today's environmental difficulties.

References

- Daptardar, V. (2012). *Gandhian relevance to environmental sustainability. Gandhi in the new millennium—Issues and challenges.*
- Dash, A. (2014). *The moral basis of sustainable society: the Gandhian concept of ecological citizenship. International Review of Sociology, 24(1), 27–37.* <https://doi.org/10.1080/03906701.2014.894343>
- Dutta, B. k. (2023, mar). *Contemporary relevance of Gandhi's ecological thought. International Journal of Humanities & Social Science Studies (IJHSSS), 9(2), 53-58.* <https://www.ijhsss.com/files/07.-Bimal-Kumar-Dutta.pdf>
- Gandhi, M. (1948). *An Autobiography: The Story of My Experiments with truth.*
- Gandhi, M. (2009). *Gandhi: "Hind Swaraj" and Other Writing Centenary Edition.* Cambridge University Press.
- Gandhi, M. K. (2021). *Key To Health: Key to Health by MK Gandhi English Edition: MK Gandhi's Insights on Achieving Optimal Health by MK Gandhi.* Prabhat Prakashan.
- Gandhi's Ashram: Seed Beds of Ecological Development. (n.d.). <https://egyankosh.ac.in/bitstream/123456789/63923/1/Block-4.pdf>
- Gandhi's views on nature and environment. (n.d.). IGNOU. <https://egyankosh.ac.in/bitstream/123456789/33724/1/Unit-16.pdf>
- Giri, S. (2023, Dec). *Gandhi and the Environment: An Exploration of His Ecological Vision and Its Relevance for Today. Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (JETIR), 10(12), 407-410.* <https://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR2312751.pdf>
- Gupta, E. D., & Kant, R. (2019). *Gandhian virtues and their relevance to health. Indian Journal of Medical Research, 149, S39-S47.*
- Hardy, D. (2021). *Mahatma Gandhi and his ashram experiments: nonviolence in international communities. International Journal on World Peace, 38(1), 69-94.*
- Joshi, D. (2003). *Gandhiji on environment. Mani Bhavan Gandhi Sangrahalaya.* https://www.mkgandhi.org/ebks/gandhiji_on_environment.pdf
- Joshi, P. (2001). *In the lap of the Himalaya: Gandhi's visit to Uttarakhand.* Retrieved from *Economic and Political Weekly*: <https://www.civildaily.com/burningissue-relevance-of-mahatma-gandhi/>
- M. K. Gandhi - C.W.M.G., Vol. - 90, Publication Division, New Delhi (1984).
- Moolakkattu, D. J. (2019, oct 01). *Mahatma Gandhi and the Environment.* Retrieved from the energy of resources institution: <https://www.teriin.org/article/mahatma-gandhi-and-environment>
- Moolakkattu, J. S. (2019, oct 01). *Gandhi at 150: Green movements have Gandhian streak.* Retrieved from *Down to earth*: <https://www.downtoearth.org.in/environment/gandhi-at-150-green-movements-have-gandhian-streak-67038>
- Parekh, B. (2001). *Gandhi: A Very Short Introduction.* OUP Oxford.

- Rajagopalan, M. R. (2001, September 24). *Gandhian view on Environment*. Retrieved from GANDHI SEVAGRAM ASHRAM: <https://www.gandhiashramsevagram.org/gandhi-articles/environmental-crisis-and-relevance-of-gandhiji.php>
- Sasikala, A. (n.d.). *Gandhi and Ecological Marxists: A Study of Silent Valley Movement*. Retrieved from Mahatma Gandhi: https://www.mkgandhi.org/articles/ecological_marxists.php
- Sasikala, A. S. (2012). *Environmental Thoughts of Gandhi for a Green Future. Notes and Comments, 51*. https://www.mkgandhi.org/ebks/Gandhi%20Marg_April_June2012.pdf#page=52
- Shiva, V. (1998). *Staying Alive: Women, ecology, and survival in India*. (Vol. 84). New Delhi: Kali for Women. p.11.
- Suchak., D. K. (n.d.). *Gandhian view on Environment*. Retrieved from GANDHI SEVAGRAM ASHRAM: <https://www.gandhiashramsevagram.org/gandhi-articles/development-and-environment-issues-with-special-reference-to-gandhian-perspective.php>
- Thomson, M. (1993). *Gandhi and his Ashrams*. London: Sangam. https://www.mkgandhi.org/ebks/Gandhi_and_his_Ashrams.pdf